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Unhealthy Psychological Environment in the Family is a Causing Factor of Domestic Violence

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***Annotation:** In this article, family violence is also the problem of violence between spouses, its study, the fact that an unhealthy psychological environment is a factor that causes violence in the origin of violence, conclusions and suggestions on how to prevent this problem is given. Violence against women in the family is manifested in the relationship between the spouses, and the specificity of such violence is the result of the gender differences of the couple, the dominant position of men and the control over the behavior of women.*

***Key words:** domestic violence, violence against women, unfavorable social situation, confrontation, adaptation, compromise, evasion, cooperation.*

Enter. The importance of studying methods of preventing violence in families in the world is related to the fact that this phenomenon affects the personal and social life of people and is a real obstacle to equality, social development and building a democratic society[1]. Currently, gender equality is officially recognized as the single value unit of modern world development, as the principles of spreading the values of peace and tolerance, respecting human dignity, and refraining from violence. In this regard, it remains an urgent task to implement a new social approach to the study of the problem of violence, to understand the conditions and consequences of social conflicts, methods of their prevention and non-violent resolution. In world educational and scientific research centers, the problems related to socio-psychological study of violence, especially family violence, and giving the necessary suggestions and recommendations aimed at preventing violence through diagnostic research are being scientifically researched. Within the framework of issues of social development, legal and regulatory frameworks aimed at protecting human rights, realizing women's rights to freedom from violence, and humanizing social relations are being created[3].

Literature review. The analysis of foreign literature shows that in the last fifty years in the West, important empirical data on the problem of family violence has been collected. In particular J.Giles-Sims and J.P.Deshner violence and its causes, M.A.Straus, R.J.Gelles, S.K.Steinmetz the development

of violence and G.Hotaling, D.B.Sugarman, B.Meloy, E.Aldarondo, etc. risk factors of violence, L.E.Walker, the impact of the dynamics of family violence on women, D.Kalmuss, the patterns of family violence transmission from generation to generation, D.G.Dutton, A.Holtzworth-Munroe, G.L.Stuart, G.Hutchison individual-psychological characteristics, N.S.Jacobson, S.A.Lloyd researched interpersonal relationships in violent situations.

Violence should be understood as a manifestation of aggression in human relations. However, each of us acts aggressively to a certain extent in different situations. Therefore, the term "violence" is an extreme form of aggression expressed in intentional, goal-directed behavior, which is expressed by the desire to intentionally enmity to cause physical or mental harm to a person, aimed at destruction or harm. Thus, the words "violence" and "aggression" are not synonymous. The first has only a destructive meaning, the second has both a destructive and a constructive meaning. Aggression can be sublimated in sports, humor, imperative tone, dominant behavior. And violence can be redirected or replaced.

L.V. Serdyuk stated that "violence is an external intentional and illegal attack on a person (or a group of persons) against or against his will, which can cause him organic, physiological and psychological injury and limit his freedom. is to show a secret[10].

One type of violence is domestic violence, which is the manifestation of violence in a relationship between a couple. The uniqueness of such violence comes from the gender differences of the couple. The concept of domestic violence applies not only to officially registered couples, but also to ex-spouses. The main difference between domestic violence and other types of violence is that domestic violence occurs between family members, in the home, in a closed social institution. R.E. Dobash, R.P. Dobash define family violence as a result of the dominant position of men and control over women's behavior [11].

Psychologists and sociologists accept and often use two classifications of violence.

The first classification is based on the nature of acts of violence and includes such types of violence as physical, sexual, psychological (emotional) and economic.

The second classification focuses on the characteristics of the object of violence, that is, age characteristics (violence against children or the elderly), gender characteristics (violence against women or men), health status (disabled or violence against the disabled), family relations (relationships between relatives), ethnic origin, profession, social status, etc.

Research Methodology. Observation, interview methods in the research, the author's questionnaire on "Study of family violence in Uzbek families", A. Bass and A. Dark's questionnaire "Study of the level of aggression", A. Thomas and R Kilman's "Determining leadership behavior in a conflict situation" method, A. Volkova's "Determining family roles and suitability for marriage" test, A. Neugarten's "Life Satisfaction Index" test-questionnaire, R. Lazarus' "Copping-test" questionnaire, L.Kulikov's "Mental state diagnosis" methodology and the SPSS program for mathematical-statistical data processing was used to determine the validity and reliability of the empirical data obtained from the research, the correlation of the methods is Spearman's r-correlation coefficient, Mann-Whitney, which identifies significant differences in the level of confidence -It was implemented according to the criteria.

Analysis and results. Research results show that the spouses of abused women are usually middle-aged, have an average level of education, and the age difference between husband and wife in such families is also large. Spouse's unemployment, low family monthly income, and husband's use of

alcohol or drugs are the characteristics of families in the experimental group. The obtained results correspond to the data of M.A.Straus, R.J.Gelles, S.K.Steinmetz, who, during a survey of 2143 families, in families characterized by male violence against women, the husband often spends half a day they found out whether they were employed or unemployed[7]. C. Mirrlees-Black studies have results on the relationship between family socioeconomic status and violence[8].

The low socio-economic status of the man in the family is one of the social factors that cause physical violence against women. This result is consistent with Goode's resource theory, which explains the occurrence of family violence. The theory goes that a family member with more resources also has more power. Also, the more resources a family member has, the less power he or she will use in relationships with others, as family violence is often used when other resources are insufficient or absent. So, a man with an average level of education, a low-paying job, a low reputation in society and weak interpersonal relationships is forced to use force to maintain his dominant position in the relationship.

Differences in the frequency of alcohol consumption by men in the family corresponded to the research results of O. V. Barnett and R. V. Fagan. According to the research results of these scientists, it was found that violent men consume alcohol frequently and in large quantities [5]. N. Rimashevskaya's research also revealed that most of the conflicts related to physical violence are the result of a man's alcohol consumption [4].

When interpreting the obtained results, it is necessary to take into account the complex physiological effects of alcohol on behavior and the inclusion of socio-cultural aspects. Researchers R. M. Tolman and L. W. Burnett studied the relationship between alcoholism and family violence, and found that the effects of alcohol, as well as the presence of violence in the parental family, personal problems, the nature of relationships found that the forms and socio-economic status of the family are determinants of violence against women [6].

The highest level of differences ($r < 0.001$) in our study was determined by the parameter "presence of stressful events in family life". According to this parameter, in families where there is violence against women, a woman or her husband loses a job or changes to another job, a serious illness of a child or other family members, a change of place of residence, a sharp decrease in family income, there are cases such as pregnancy or childbirth, children's offenses at school or other educational institution, problems with the law of the husband or wife. The presence of "disagreement" between the husband's parents and the wife's relationship, which is common in the families of the experimental group, can be considered as an additional stress factor.

Conclusion/Recommendations.

1. Unfavorable social situation (husband not working, low total family income) forms interpersonal relations that lead to acts of violence against women.
2. Negative behavior models observed in the woman's parental family
3. The presence of negative examples of interpersonal relationships in the husband's parental family increases the likelihood of violent behavior against women.
4. The presence of violence against women in the family contributes to the formation of incompatible forms of behavior, including opposite behaviors such as "cooperative" and "aggressive". Women who experience more severe and recurrent violence exhibit behaviors associated with greater conformity, agreement, cooperation, and compromise.

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